

Use of Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system in photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion and storage

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Abstract : Photogalvanic effect was studied in cell containing Bromocresol green as photosensitizer in ascorbic acid-NaLS system. The conversion efficiency of the cell, fill factor and the cell performance were observed 0.80%, 0.23 and 140.0 min in dark respectively. The effects of different parameters on the electrical output of the cell were observed and current-voltage (i-V) characteristics of the cell were also studied. The photopotential and photocurrent were observed as 834 mV and 350 μ A respectively. The mechanism was proposed for the generation of photocurrent in photogalvanic cell.

Keywords : Bromocresol green, ascorbic acid, sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), photogalvanic effect, fill factor, conversion efficiency.

Introduction

The reserve of fossil fuels and wood are depleting very fast, as a results of which energy production is becoming expensive day by day. The search for alternative source of energy has led to rapid strides in the utilization of solar energy¹. Conversion of solar energy into electrical energy through photogalvanic cell is the most important and desirable route for obtaining electricity.

The photogalvanic cell works on photogalvanic effect. This effect was reported by Rideal and Williams² but it was systematically investigated by Rabinowitch^{3,4}. Later on many workers studied it from time to time⁵⁻¹¹. Ameta *et al.*¹²⁻¹⁵ reported the photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion and storage. Use of micelles in photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion and storage : cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide-glucose-toluidine blue system studied by Gangotri *et al.*¹⁶. Comparative studies in anionic, cationic and neutral surfactants in Azur-B-NTA-CPC system in photogalvanic cell was reported by Genwa and Gangotri¹⁷. Role of surfactants in photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion and storage studied by Gangotri and Bhimwal¹⁸. Recently, Genwa and Sagar¹⁹ and Genwa and Chauhan²⁰ reported some new photogalvanic cell systems in view of electrical parameters and solar energy conversion and storage. The

present work is an effort to increase the efficiency of photogalvanic cell using Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system in photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion and storage.

Results and discussion

Absorption properties of photosensitizer and surfactant :

It was observed that the photosensitizer (Bromocresol green) shows absorption peak (λ_{\max}) in visible region with maximum at 615 nm. Absorption spectrum of photosensitizer after adding known concentration of surfactant solution was also taken. The concentration of Bromocresol green and NaLS solution for the experiment were kept at ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$) and NaLS ($1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$) respectively. The changes in the spectra are shown in Fig. 1.

Effect of variation of Bromocresol green, ascorbic acid and NaLS concentration :

The results showing the effect of variation of Bromocresol green, ascorbic acid and NaLS concentration are summarized in Table 1. Variation of dye concentration studied by using solution of Bromocresol green of different concentrations. It was observed that the photopotential and photocurrent increased with increase in concentra-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Bromocresol green.

Table 1. Effect of variation of Bromocresol green, ascorbic acid and NaLS concentrations

Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , Temperature = 303 K

Concentrations	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μA)
[Bromocresol green] $\times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$		
0.8	732.0	288.0
1.2	785.0	318.0
1.6	834.0	350.0
1.9	795.0	308.0
2.4	698.0	242.0
[Ascorbic acid] $\times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$		
0.7	738.0	278.0
0.9	785.0	312.0
1.1	834.0	350.0
1.4	776.0	306.0
1.6	702.0	262.0
[NaLS] $\times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$		
0.8	712.0	285.0
1.0	768.0	323.0
1.2	834.0	350.0
1.4	778.0	318.0
1.7	723.0	276.0

tion of the dye [Bromocresol green]. A maxima (at 834 mV and 350 μA) was obtained for a particular value of dye concentration ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$), above which a decrease in electrical output of the cell was observed. Low electrical output observed at the lower concentration range of dye due to limited number of dye molecules to absorb the major portion of the light in the path, while higher concentration of dye again resulted in a decrease in electrical output because intensity of light reaching the molecule near the electrode decrease due to absorption of the major portion of the light by the dye molecules present in the path, therefore corresponding fall in the electric output of the cell. Reductant concentration also affects the cell output. With the increase in concentration of the reductant [Ascorbic acid], the photopotential and photocurrent was found to increase till it reaches a maximum value at $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. These values are 834 mV and 350 μA respectively. On further increase in concentration of ascorbic acid, a decrease in the electrical output of the cell was observed. The fall in power output was also resulted with decrease in concentration of reductant due to less number of molecules available for electron donation to the cat-

ionic form of dye. On the other hand, the movement of dye molecules hindered by the higher concentration of reductant to reach the electrode in the desired time limit and it will also result in to a decrease in electrical output. The electrical output of the cell was increased on increasing the concentration of surfactant [NaLS]. A maximum (834 mV and 350 μ A) result was obtained at a certain value (1.2×10^{-3} M) of concentration of NaLS. On further increasing the surfactant concentration it react as a barrier and major portion of the surfactant photobleach the less number of dye molecules so that a down fall in electrical output was observed.

Effect of pH :

Photogalvanic cell containing Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system was found to be quite sensitive to pH of the solution. It was observed that the increase in photopotential and photocurrent of the cell with increase in pH value (in alkaline range). At pH 11.60 a maxima (834 mV and 350 μ A) was achieved. On further increase in pH, there was a decrease photopotential and photocurrent. The optimum electrical output was obtained at particular pH value. It may be due to better availability of reductant's donor form at that pH value. The results showing the effect of pH are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of pH

[Bromocresol green] = 1.6×10^{-5} M, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm⁻², [Ascorbic acid] = 1.1×10^{-3} M, Temperature = 303 K, [NaLS] = 1.2×10^{-3} M

pH	Photopotential	Photocurrent
	(mV)	(μ A)
11.45	728.0	278.0
11.52	776.0	322.0
11.60	834.0	350.0
11.68	784.0	305.0
11.75	712.0	248.0

Effect of diffusion length and electrode area :

Effect of variation of diffusion length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameter of the cell (i_{max}) was studied by using H-shaped cells of different dimensions. It was observed that in the first few minutes of illuminations there is sharp increase in the photocurrent. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) increase with increase in diffusion length because

path for photochemical reaction was increased, but this is not observed experimentally. Whereas equilibrium photocurrent (i_{eq}) decreased linearly. Therefore, it may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi form of dye (photosensitizer) in the illuminated and dark chamber respectively. The reductant and its oxidation product act only as electron carriers in the path. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of diffusion length

[Bromocresol green] = 1.6×10^{-5} M, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm⁻², [Ascorbic acid] = 1.1×10^{-3} M, Temperature = 303 K, [NaLS] = 1.2×10^{-3} M, pH = 11.60

Diffusion length D_L (mm)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μ A)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μ A)	Rate of initial generation of current (μ A min ⁻¹)
35	432.0	358.0	11.37
40	436.0	354.0	11.47
45	440.0	350.0	11.58
50	444.0	346.0	11.68
55	448.0	342.0	11.79

The effect of electrode area on the current parameters of the cell was also studied. It was observed that with the increase in the electrode area the value of maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) is found to increase. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of electrode area

[Bromocresol green] = 1.6×10^{-5} M, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm⁻², [Ascorbic acid] = 1.1×10^{-3} M, Temperature = 303 K, [NaLS] = 1.2×10^{-3} M, pH = 11.60

Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system	Electrode area (cm ²)				
	0.70	0.85	1.00	1.15	1.30
Maximum photocurrent					
i_{max} (μ A)	428.0	435.0	440.0	446.0	452.0
Equilibrium photocurrent					
i_{eq} (μ A)	362.0	355.0	350.0	342.0	335.0

Effect of light intensity :

The intensity of light was also affects the electrical output of the cell. It was observed that photocurrent shows a linear increasing behavior with the increase in light intensity whereas photopotential increased in logarithmic manner. This increasing behavior of electrical output due to increase in number of photons with increase in light

Fig. 2. Variation of photocurrent and log V with light intensity.

intensity. The effect of variation of light intensity on the photopotential and photocurrent is graphically represented in Fig. 2.

i-V Characteristics :

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of the photogalvanic cell were measured under the continuous illumination of light, with the help of digital pH meter (keeping the circuit open) and a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed) respectively. The potential and current in between these two extreme values (V_{pp} and i_{pp}) were recorded with the help of a carbon pot (log 407 K) connected in the circuit of microammeter through which an external load applied. i - V characteristics of the cell containing Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system is shown in current-potential curve (Fig. 3). It was observed that i - V curve deviated from its regular rectangular shape. A point in the i - V curve, called power point (pp), was determined where the product of curve of current and potential was maximum. With the help of i - V curve, the fill-factor was calculated as 0.23 using the formula :

$$\text{Fill factor } (\eta) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

Cell performance and conversion efficiency :

The performance of the photogalvanic cell was observed by applying an external load (necessary to have current at power point) after termination the illumination as soon as the potential reaches a constant value. The performance was determined in terms of $t_{1/2}$, i.e. the time required in fall of the output (power) to its half at power point in dark. It was observed that the cell can be used in dark for 140.0 min. Performance of the cell is graphically shown in time-power curve (Fig. 4). Conversion efficiency of the cell was determined as 0.80%, using the formula :

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{A \times 10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}} \quad (2)$$

Mechanism :

When certain dyes are excited by the light in the presence of electron donating substance (reductant), the dyes

Fig. 3. Current-potential (i-V) curve of the cell.

Fig. 4. Time-power curve.

are rapidly changed into colorless form. The dye now acts as a powerful reducing agent and can donate electron to other substance and reconverted to its oxidized state²¹. On the basis of earlier studies²² a tentative mechanism in the photogalvanic cell may be proposed as follows :

Illumination chamber :

On irradiation, dye molecule get excited :

The excited dye molecule accepts an electron from reductant and converted into semi or leuco form of dye and the reductant into its excited state :

At platinum electrode :

The semi or leuco form of dye loses an electron and converted into original dye molecule :

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode :

Finally semi/leuco form of dye and oxidized form of reductant combine to give original dye and reductant molecule and the cycle will go on :

Here Dye, Dye*, Dye⁻, R and R⁺ are the dye, its excited form, leuco form, reductant and its oxidized form, respectively. Scheme of mechanism is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Scheme of mechanism.

Experimental

Materials :

Bromocresol green (98%, Loba Chemie, Mumbai), ascorbic acid (99.9%, Ases Chemical, Jodhpur), NaLS (99%, Sisco Research Laboratories, Mumbai) and sodium

hydroxide (96%, RFCL, New Delhi) were used in the present work. Solutions of ascorbic acid, Bromocresol green, NaLS and NaOH (1 M) were prepared in double distilled water (conductivity $3.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Sm}^{-1}$) and kept in amber coloured containers to protect them from sun light.

Bromocresol green dye (Scheme 1) is crystalline powder brown in color, odorless, soluble in water and stable under normal temperatures and pressures. Its molecular formula and molecular weight $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{Br}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$ and 698.01 respectively. Melting point and density of dye measured in laboratory and find about 225 °C and 0.79 g/mL respectively.

Scheme 1. Bromocresol green.

Method :

A mixture of solutions of dye (Bromocresol green), reductant (ascorbic acid), surfactant (NaLS) and NaOH was taken in an H-type glass tube which was blackened by black carbon paper to unaffected from sun radiation. A shiny platinum foil electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) was immersed in one limb of the H-tube and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was immersed in the other limb. Platinum electrode act as a working electrode and SCE as a counter electrode. The whole system was first placed in the dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing the platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips). A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiation. Photochemical bleaching of the dye was studied potentiometrically. Absorption spectra of dye-surfactant combination was noted by using spectrophotometer (Systronics 106) with the matched pair of silica cuvetts (path length 1 cm). All spectral measurements were duplicated in a constant temperature water bath

maintained with in ± 1 °C and mean values were processed for data analysis.

A digital pH meter (Systronics 335) was used to measure the potential and a microammeter (Nucon) was used to measure the current generated by the system respectively. The current voltage characteristics were studied by applying an external load with the help of a carbon pot (log 470 K) connected in the circuit. Over all experimental set up is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Experimental set up.

Conclusions :

The photogalvanic conversion of solar energy has attracted attention of scientists towards solar energy conversion and storage. This cell undergoes cyclical charging and discharging process. The charging of cell occurs only in presence of illuminating source. The discharging of cell takes place only when we apply the external circuit for electron transfer. As long as there is no external circuit, the cell will keep light energy stored. The photogalvanic cell have inbuilt storage capacity and stored energy can be used in absence of light whereas photovoltaic cells needs extra hardware as batteries for energy storage, photogalvanic cells are economic than photovoltaic cells because low cost materials are used in these cells. The conversion efficiency, storage capacity and fill factor are recorded as 0.80%, $t_{1/2}$ 140.0 min and 0.23 respectively in Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system.

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